

TDD anti patterns - Survey focused on the industry and developer experience

Hello there, first of all, thanks for taking the time to answer this survey. It means you will be part of the picture on the TDD (Test Driven Development) anti patterns across the industry, which will help us to push further the quality on software development. Gathering data around that allows us to better understand how to improve it.

This survey has the goal of collect the data regarding the TDD practice on the industry that leads to anti patterns regardless of the years of experience practicing it, the focus is on drawing an image from the ground up, no matter the experience level, so don't worry if you have never used TDD before, you can still fill in the survey.

Besides that, this survey is anonymous and has 23 questions divided into 6 sections. The data collected here is not specific in a level that makes possible to identify who filled in, and the data used here will be used only for publishing the results in papers or presentations.

If you want to, in the end you can offer a contact email to be notified when such results are published.

If you have any question regarding this survey, or my inspiration to do that, have a look at this blog post I wrote <https://marabesi.com/thoughts/2021/07/28/tdd-revamped-five-years-and-many-more-to-come.html> please contact me @MatheusMarabesi

* Required

Professional background

This section focus on your background and where you worked at as well as the programming languages you are familiar with. The focus here is to understand better which programming languages you are using to work in a professional environment.

1. I am a software developer working in the industry professionally for: *

Mark only one oval.

- I have no experience in professional projects
- Less than one year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- Between 3 and 5 years
- Between 5 and 10 years
- Between 10 and 20 years
- Between 20 and 30 years
- 30 years or more

2. I work/worked for projects in the following countries (list provided by <https://www.listofcountriesoftheworld.com/>):

*

Check all that apply.

- Afghanistan
- Akrotiri
- Albania
- Algeria
- American Samoa
- Andorra
- Angola
- Anguilla
- Antarctica
- Antigua and Barbuda
- Argentina
- Armenia
- Aruba
- Ashmore and Cartier Islands
- Australia
- Austria
- Azerbaijan
- Bahamas, The
- Bahrain
- Bangladesh
- Barbados
- Bassas da India
- Belarus
- Belgium
- Belize
- Benin
- Bermuda
- Bhutan
- Bolivia
- Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Botswana
- Bouvet Island
- Brazil
- British Indian Ocean Territory
- British Virgin Islands
- Brunei

- Bulgaria
- Burkina Faso
- Burma
- Burundi
- Cambodia
- Cameroon
- Canada
- Cape Verde
- Cayman Islands
- Central African Republic
- Chad
- Chile
- China
- Christmas Island
- Clipperton Island
- Cocos (Keeling) Islands
- Colombia
- Comoros
- Congo, Democratic Republic of the
- Congo, Republic of the
- Cook Islands
- Coral Sea Islands
- Costa Rica
- Cote d'Ivoire
- Croatia
- Cuba
- Cyprus
- Czech Republic
- Denmark
- Dhekelia
- Djibouti
- Dominica
- Dominican Republic
- Ecuador
- Egypt
- El Salvador
- Equatorial Guinea
- Eritrea
- Estonia
- Ethiopia

- Europa Island
- Falkland Islands (Islas Malvinas)
- Faroe Islands
- Fiji
- Finland
- France
- French Guiana
- French Polynesia
- French Southern and Antarctic Lands
- Gabon
- Gambia, The
- Gaza Strip
- Georgia
- Germany
- Ghana
- Gibraltar
- Glorioso Islands
- Greece
- Greenland
- Grenada
- Guadeloupe
- Guam
- Guatemala
- Guernsey
- Guinea
- Guinea-Bissau
- Guyana
- Haiti
- Heard Island and McDonald Islands
- Holy See (Vatican City)
- Honduras
- Hong Kong
- Hungary
- Iceland
- India
- Indonesia
- Iran
- Iraq
- Ireland
- Isle of Man

- Israel
- Italy
- Jamaica
- Jan Mayen
- Japan
- Jersey
- Jordan
- Juan de Nova Island
- Kazakhstan
- Kenya
- Kiribati
- Korea, North
- Korea, South
- Kuwait
- Kyrgyzstan
- Laos
- Latvia
- Lebanon
- Lesotho
- Liberia
- Libya
- Liechtenstein
- Lithuania
- Luxembourg
- Macau
- Macedonia
- Madagascar
- Malawi
- Malaysia
- Maldives
- Mali
- Malta
- Marshall Islands
- Martinique
- Mauritania
- Mauritius
- Mayotte
- Mexico
- Micronesia, Federated States of
- Moldova

- Monaco
- Mongolia
- Montenegro
- Montserrat
- Morocco
- Mozambique
- Namibia
- Nauru
- Navassa Island
- Nepal
- Netherlands
- Netherlands Antilles
- New Caledonia
- New Zealand
- Nicaragua
- Niger
- Nigeria
- Niue
- Norfolk Island
- Northern Mariana Islands
- Norway
- Oman
- Pakistan
- Palau
- Panama
- Papua New Guinea
- Paracel Islands
- Paraguay
- Peru
- Philippines
- Pitcairn Islands
- Poland
- Portugal
- Puerto Rico
- Qatar
- Reunion
- Romania
- Russia
- Rwanda
- Saint Helena

- Saint Kitts and Nevis
- Saint Lucia
- Saint Pierre and Miquelon
- Saint Vincent and the Grenadines
- Samoa
- San Marino
- Sao Tome and Principe
- Saudi Arabia
- Senegal
- Serbia
- Seychelles
- Sierra Leone
- Singapore
- Slovakia
- Slovenia
- Solomon Islands
- Somalia
- South Africa
- South Georgia and the South Sandwich Islands
- Spain
- Spratly Islands
- Sri Lanka
- Sudan
- Suriname
- Svalbard
- Swaziland
- Sweden
- Switzerland
- Syria
- Taiwan
- Tajikistan
- Tanzania
- Thailand
- Timor-Leste
- Togo
- Tokelau
- Tonga
- Trinidad and Tobago
- Tromelin Island
- Tunisia

- Turkey
- Turkmenistan
- Turks and Caicos Islands
- Tuvalu
- Uganda
- Ukraine
- United Arab Emirates
- United Kingdom
- United States
- Uruguay
- Uzbekistan
- Vanuatu
- Venezuela
- Vietnam
- Virgin Islands
- Wake Island
- Wallis and Futuna
- West Bank
- Western Sahara
- Yemen
- Zambia
- Zimbabwe

3. I write/wrote code professionally in the following languages (programming languages listed are from <https://www.tiobe.com/tiobe-index>):

*

Check all that apply.

- C
- Python
- Java
- C++
- C#
- Visual Basic
- Javascript
- Assembly language
- PHP
- SQL
- Groovy
- Ruby
- GO
- Swift
- MATLAB
- Fortran
- R
- Perl
- Delphi
- Objective C
- Scala
- Kotlin
- Lisp
- Dart
- Lua
- Typescript
- Haskell
- Rust
- Closure
- Other

4. I am familiar with testing tools such as Junit, Jest, PHPUnit or any other framework * that provides a common ground to write tests.

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

TDD practices on the daily basis

This section focuses on your professional practices, meaning that the questions that follows are related to your daily work. Questions regarding TDD means:

- I write the test code first before the production code.

5. I learned TDD at work *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

6. I learned TDD myself, through books, videos courses or tutorials. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

7. People that I work/worked with already knew TDD *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

8. The people I work with practice TDD as part of daily work *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

9. I practice TDD as part of my daily workflow. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

10. I feel that TDD makes me go slower than if I wasn't doing it *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

TDD practices at companies I worked at

11. I am not allowed to push code for review without a test case with it *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

12. The companies I work/worked at, required TDD to join them as part of the job description. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

13. Companies I work/worked at do not practice TDD *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

14. Companies I work/worked at argued that TDD requires more time to complete a task and the teams didn't have the required time to use it. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

15. Companies I work/worked at value the TDD practice and acknowledge its pros and cons *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Anti patterns

This section focuses on the TDD anti patterns and how you is familiar with it. TDD anti patterns are a list of 22 anti patterns listed by James Carr, in which he depicts the issues that are related to hard to maintain test code and slow tests suites, leading to slower feedback.

16. I can recall in my mind at least one TDD anti pattern *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

17. From the following list check the anti patterns you can recall

Check all that apply.

- The liar
- The giant
- The mockery
- The inspector
- Generous leftovers
- The local hero
- The nitpicker
- The secret catcher
- The dodger
- Oudmouth
- The greedy catcher
- Excessive setup
- The sequencer
- Hidden dependency
- The enumerator
- The stranger
- The operating system evangelist
- Success against all odds
- The free ride
- The one
- The peeping tom
- The slow poke

18. I could spot at least one TDD anti pattern in the code base I work/worked on professionally. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

19. I feel that TDD anti patterns slows me down *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

20. When I tried to practice TDD in a code base without tests, I felt that I was slowed down by writing the test first. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

21. I write test because I am worried about the code coverage *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

22. I write tests, but without TDD because the project I am working on demands tests. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Finishing up

23. If you want to be notified when the results are published, leave your email address on the box that follows.

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Google.

Google Forms

